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Determination of the content of Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd in the river Shkumbin (Pena) with potentiometric analysis stripping

Bujar H. Durmishi^{1*}, Shemsedin Abduli¹, Arianit A. Reka¹, Murtezan Ismaili¹,
Agim Shabani¹, Arbana Durmishi¹

¹University of Tetovo, Faculty of Mathematical-Natural Sciences, Department of Chemistry,
Ss. Ilindenip.n., 1200 Tetovo, R. of Macedonia

*Corresponding author: bujar.durmishi@unite.edu.mk

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Abstract

Environmental pollution occupies an important place of surface water pollution. The use of contaminated water directly affects human health and causes long-term consequences. The most common pollutant in rivers are heavy metals such as Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd. They contribute significantly to the pollution of the aquatic environment as they don't biodegradable and some of them have cumulative toxic properties. Heavy metals can cause many disorders and threaten human health because accumulate in certain organs. The purpose of this research was to determine the content of Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd in the river Shkumbin, Republic of Macedonia. Water samples were taken at four site-sampling (SH1, SH2, SH3 and SH4) for the period January to December 2002. Heavy metals are determined by potentiometric stripping analysis, while some results are compared with atomic absorption spectrometry. The research found that in one year, the river has been more restrained Zn, and Cu, Pb and Cd were not detected. The average annual content of Zn standard deviation was 0.0227 ± 0.0157 mg / L with range 0.0060 - 0.0748 mg / L. The average standard deviation values of the concentration of Zn in the winter, spring, summer and autumn were, 0.0252 ± 0.0099 mg / L, 0.0294 ± 0.0271 mg / L, 0.0172 ± 0.0058 mg / L and 0.0192 ± 0.0088 mg / L, respectively. The most contaminated sample site was SH4. From the results we conclude that the river for this period have not been contaminated with heavy metals fall into the first category, compared with the European Regulation and the Regulation of the Republic of Macedonia official.

Keywords: potentiometric stripping analysis, surface water quality, river Shkumbin (Pena), heavy metals, atomic absorption spectrometry.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the major world problems is a drastic reduction of water resources [1]. Nowadays many people worldwide suffer from the lack of safe and quality water, which is essential for popular needs. In many countries, water resources are depleted faster than they can be renewed and not enough for the demands of modern human life. The main factors that pollute the water are: population growth, the development of many branches of industry, the intensive farming practices etc. So, this problem is getting worse day by day due to demographic growth sputtering, which is directly related to the contamination of water sources. But population growth and industrial development should not be factors of water pollution. Pollution becomes only due to carelessness and ignorance, or the desire of owners of enterprises for greater earnings. In this regard, environmental protection becomes increasingly demand greater for the survival of human civilization [2].

Polluting the marine environment are heavy metals in natural waters which come mainly drawn from anthropogenic activities by contaminating aquatic ecosystems along the time. Consequently, heavy metals present a significant source of deteriorating health and life of living things plant, animal and human. Although it is difficult classification of heavy metals in essential and toxic metals, however it is well known that an essential metal becomes toxic at very high concentrations.

Determination of heavy metals in surface waters has become an important part of many studies related to environmental pollution and health hazards. Therefore, exposure of heavy metals through consumption of water and aquatic products presents a potential risk to human health. Thus, research on the presence of heavy metals in fish have increased in the last decade worldwide [3].

According to the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), lead, cadmium, copper and zinc are some of the heavy metals that pollute common [4]. Heavy metals can cause many disorders and threaten human health as a result of their accumulation in organs such as liver and kidney in long periods of time. It is known that the main targets of Pb and Cd are the nervous system and kidneys. The role of heavy metals such as Cu and Zn to human health can be significantly associated with their role essential for many enzymatic functions; however, their taking more than the recommended safe levels can produce toxic effects [5-7].

The most common trace metal pollutants to the aquatic environment are: Cu, Zn, Pb, Cd, Hg, Ni, Cr and As. These metals are commonly used in the industry and can cause health problems if taken in high concentrations. Nevertheless, metal traces have biological availability unless the metal is in its soluble, where the speed of hydrolysis of the metal traces present in water depends on the balance of the anion and cation, the redox potential and pH of these waters, as well as size distribution and chemical nature of the deposit particles [8].

Methods and common analytical techniques used for the determination of heavy metals in trace are: spectrometric methods (emission and absorption) and electro-

analytical methods. Electrochemical stripping analysis (AES) is a rare technique elektroanalitike, which with high sensitivity enables the determination of trace metals in water. AES does not need preparation of the samples, which hinders contamination, loss or change in physico-chemical properties of the analyte. AES also possible to determine various selective oxidizing conditions of an item that has special significance for determination of reactivity, transport and comprehensive industry-dropping poisoning [9-13].

Potentiometric stripping analysis (APS) as AES technique is characterized by sensitivity and simplicity. APS, among others, is used in the analysis where is been made the determination of cations, and anions and compounds in aqueous systems. With the development and progress of computer technology in analytical instruments, it decreased sensitivity difference between APS and AES. The fact that the first phase of AES analysis is virtually the same for all stripping techniques, then the conditions of electrolysis of an item, defined for stripping voltammetric techniques are virtually the same for APS. The APS should be determined only necessary electrolysis time.

APS is electro-analytical technique that is performed in two steps. The first step involves electro-lysis of metal ions, which are dissolved in the electrode mercury coated with carbon vitreous, while the second step is called stripping includes re-oxidation chemical metal deposit. APS first introduced in 1976 by Janger and Graneli. The authors demonstrated the possibility of chemical oxidation of the deposit created on the working electrode of mercury ions (II) [14]. Deposit metal is formed as defined voltammetric techniques in the solution electrolysis at constant potential during intensive mixing of the solution. During digestion followed deposit is working electrode potential, and in potenciogramin acquired ($E-\tau$) has the potential of showing characteristic digestive kualitative, digestive and characterized kuantitatitve time (Fig. 2). The metal is determined by the method addment of standard or calibration curve.

APS allows the determination of some trace metals in complex matrices in a wide concentration range, since it is less susceptible to interference absorber on the surface of the electrode, compared with other electro-analytical techniques [15-18]. Another great advantage of APS is that it allows the analysis of the sample without removing dissolved oxygen, thus enabling its use as oxidizing agent. Both advantages are due to the fact that low currents are applied during the re-oxidation [19].

Although there is a rich scientific literature on the content of heavy metals in the rivers of the world, it is apparent lack of such data for the River Shkumbin (Pena). Therefore, this study aimed at researching the contents of Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd in the river Shkumbin, Macedonia to assess the annual variation of the content of metals mentioned.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. The study area

Macedonia is located in the central part of the Balkan Peninsula, where the environmental situation can be compared to the other countries of Central and Eastern Europe [20]. In Macedonia, the largest amount of water located in its western part. Macedonia does not have sufficient water resources and their absence is felt now in certain periods [21]. In Macedonia, the state water quality shows that the natural balance in the flow of water has deteriorated since now because of the pollution of rivers with toxic organic compounds, heavy metals, pesticides, etc. Pollution is so great, especially in the waters that come after cities, where large amounts of cities and industries contribute also their urban waters. Macedonia cleaned very little urban waters. In comparison with other rivers in the country, Vardar river is quite polluted by urban and industrial pollution.

River Shkumbin (Pena) - Tetovo river (the old name Artat) has a great importance in the development of Tetovo and not only that. It is the largest branch of the river Vardar from Sharri Mountain and has a length of about 29.7 km, the difference in height of 1914 m. Shkumbin River originates in the mountains of Sharr, from villages Bozovce and Veshala. Shkumbini passes through the town of Tetovo and then flows after the village Saraqine in the river Vardar (Fig. 1). The local economic importance of the river lies in its use in various branches of industry, agricultural irrigation Pollog part in urban development, recreation, while less for fishing and water sports. Unfortunately, in the Shkumbin River the wastewater are effluent discharged from the city and some villages without prior collector cleanup. We think that this issue is an urgent priority for municipal and state authorities should positively resolved as soon as possible.

Pic. 1. Map of place-sampling

2.2. The take of samples, reagents and instruments

Experimental part of this research is carried out in the laboratories of the Centre for Public Health in the city of Tetovo, while measurements of atomic absorption spectrometry (SAA) were performed in the laboratory of Peja (Republic of Kosovo), due to lack of instrument. For analysis were used different chemicals, which have been of the chemical purity "pro analy-sis", while some suprapur. For rational reasons we will not mention them.

This research was conducted monitoring for one year (2002) the contents of Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd in the river Shkumbin Tetovo, Macedonia. Samples were taken at four sampling points that each month to determine the extent of contamination with heavy metals and other effluents. Site-sampling (sampling stations) were as follows: the village Brodec-SH1, SH2 th Banja Hisar (under Sellce), SH3 - under the Hospital of Tetovo and SH4 Saraqine th village (Fig. 1) samples. The take of samples was made after a previous study of the river and site-sampling. Serious account is held for the distance between the site-sampling in order to enable the extraction of logical conclusions from the results obtained and their mutual comparing. Tools and utensils used for sampling standard.

Heavy metals (Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd) are defined by APS. For their determination in samples of water Shkumbin it is used Stripping analyzer M1 produced by the company Elu-Leskovac in cooperation with the Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, year of manufacture 1989; while measuring controlling metals mentioned is made by Buck Scientific Model 200A Absorbcion Atomic Spectrophotometer American production, production year 1999, laboratory Peja.

2.3. Methods of determining the APS

In APS the metal content is determined by adding the standard method (most often) or calibration curve method (rarely). The method of calibration curve applies only in the case of analysis with simple matrix. In this case APS expires after oxidation without adding standard. The first method, prior to the addition of the elements of the standard liquids "Found" the analytic need to name them. The instrument, after typing the command "I" without "shift" should be written symbol of the element, the volume and concentration of liquids with the increased standards [22].

If the analytic has no information on the potential elements of a solution or the unknown sample analyzes, it is best to become the pre-analysis of standard solution with the addition of elements which are supposed to be present. Increasing the time of oxidation is certain qualitative evidence. After naming the elements in solution included standard and their solutions in terms of like APS cycle repeated.

After the completion of this phase, the analytic indicator M1 can read concentrations of the elements named. The volume of standard solution must be at most 0.5 mL, as the volume of initial solution does not change significantly. The concentration of added standard solution must be determined so that after repeating the quantitative analysis of double features (Fig. 2). We should be careful to stay within the standard liquids (depending on concentration) and their purity. Standard solutions should be stored in polyethylene bottles.

Fig. 2. Potentiogram by APS

2.4. Determination of heavy metals with APS

Determination of Zn: Zn for determining the first set of electrolysis conditions on M1 analyzer (Tab. 1). Sample of river water about 100 mL of water filtered by the filter paper with black tape. Pipette deal with 20 mL of water filtered and placed in glass analyzer (in the same solution set of four heavy metals: Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd). Automatic micro-pipette to add about 35-40 μ L in HCl concentration known to be pH 1.2 (the pH value is determined this Cu, Cd and Pb). We check that with the universal reagent paper. After this solution is placed in the analyzer cups and given appropriate commands to start electrolysis. The oxidation potential is determined by which of ions is present in solution (Table 2). Then follows pauses and finally oxidation of Zn. Determination of Zn becomes the internal standard method. Therefore the solution is added to the beaker with 5 l in micro-pipet with standard solution of Zn (NO₃)₂ with the known concentration. This is done to double the time of electrolysis (double the potential-time curve). The analyzer provides the result in g / L, which together with the potential-time curve is printed with the printer that is connected with it. Zn oxidation potential is 900-1009 mV. Characteristic values of the potentials of Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd in puferin acetate and HCl are given in Table 2.

Table 1. Conditions of determining Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd with APS

Parameters	Pb, Cu	Cd, Zn
Potential of electrolysis, Ag / AgCl / KCl (3.5 mol / L) (V)	-0.962	-1.522
Final Potential , Ag / AgCl / KCl (3.5 mol / L) (V)	0	-0.15
The sample volume (mL)	20	20
The duration of the break (s)	15	15
The speed of mixing solution (rrpm)	4000	4000
Extension of electrolysis (s)	60-600	60-900

Table 2. Potentials digestive characteristic for Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd during APS (in volts)

Acetat buffer (pH = 4.7)		HCl (pH = 1.2)	
metal	$U_{\text{work.-refer.}}$	metal	$U_{\text{work.-refer.}}$
Zn	-1.035	Cd	-0.590
Cd	-0.607	Pb	-0.415
Pb	-0.452	Cu	-0.105

Determination of Cu, for determining of Cu the first set of electrolysis conditions on M1 analyzer (Tab. 1). Sample of river water about 100 mL of water filtered by the filter paper with black tape. Pipette of deal with 20 mL of water filtered and placed in a glass of analyst M1 (in the same solution set of four heavy metals: Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd). With automatic mikropipette added about 35-40 l in HCl concentration known to be pH 1.2 (the pH value is determined this Cu, Cd and Pb). We check that with the universal reagent paper. After this solution is placed in the analyzer cups and given appropriate commands to start electrolysis. The oxidation potential is determined by which of ions is present in solution (Tab. 2). Then follows pauses and finally oxidation of Cu. Determination of Cu done by internal standard method. Therefore the solution is added to the beaker with 5 l in mikropipette standard solution of Cu (NO₃)₂ known concentration. This is done to double the time of electrolysis (double the potential-time curve). The analyzer provides the result in g / L, which together with the potential-time curve is printed with the printer that is connected with it. The oxidation potential of Cu is around 100-120 mV.

Determination of Pb, for determining the Pb we firstly set the electrolysis conditions on M1 analyzer (Tab. 1). From the sample of river water about 100 mL of water is filtered by the filter paper with black tape. With pipette are taken 20 mL of water filtered and placed in glass analyzer (in the same solution set of four heavy metals: Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd). With automatic mikropipette added about 35-40 l in HCl concentration known to be pH 1.2 (the pH value is determined this Cu, Cd and Pb). We check that with the universal reagent paper. After this solution is placed in the analyzer cups and given appropriate commands to start electrolysis. The oxidation potential is determined by which of ions is present in solution (Tab. 2). Then follows pauses and finally oxidation of Pb. Determination of Pb becomes the internal standard method. Therefore the solution is added to the glass with 5µL mikropipette standard solution of Pb (NO₃)₂ known concentration. This is done to double the time of electrolysis (double the potential-time curve). The analyzer provides the result in g / L, which together with the potential-time curve is printed with the printer that is connected with it. Pb oxidation potential is about 415-460 mV.

Determination of Cd, for determining the Cd firstly we set the electrolysis conditions on M1 analyzer (Tab. 1). From the sample of river water about 100 mL of water is filtered by the filter paper with black tape. With Pipette are taken 20 mL of filtered water and placed in glass analyzer (in the same solution set of four heavy metals: Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd). With automatic mikropipette added about 35-40 l in HCl concentration known to be pH 1.2 (the pH value is determined this Cu, Cd and Pb). We check that the universal reagent paper. After this solution is placed in the analyzer cups and given appropriate commands to start electrolysis. The oxidation potential is determined by which of ions is present in solution (Tab. 2).

Then follows pauses and finally oxidation of Cd. Determination of Cd becomes the internal standard method. Therefore the solution is added to the beaker with 5 l in mikropipette standard solution of Cd (NO₃)₂ known concentration. This is done to double the time of electrolysis (double the potential-time curve). The analyzer provides the result in g / L and with potential-time curve is printed with the printer that is connected with it. Cd oxidation potential is about 600 mV.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Metals in surface waters

Heavy metals have a special importance to surface water pollution. Concentrations of some of them are useful, while others are harmful and toxic. Some metals such as Ca and Mg are essential chemical elements, while other metals adversely affect water consumers. It is proved that Pb, Hg, and As are strong pollutants and toxic [23]. Al, Zn and Sn are part of tin for packing foods canned, can be taken as non harmful. Toxicity of heavy metals depends on the type of metal and compound, the amount that reaches the body and the duration of action of metal. In this group belong metals, Hg, Pb, Cd, Cr, Cu, Ni, As and Zn.

To remove traces of metals from sediments rivers in the adsorption process is responsible and has recently become more research in this process. Suspended particles in aqueous systems are of different size and sediment held a variable time, and they consist of various organic substances and inorganic [24].

Zn-is found in natural waters in larger quantities compared with Cu, Pb, Cd and Hg, so the industrial discharge waters containing high concentrations of it. Zn is not accumulated in the body and it is activating enzymes. It affects bone growth, development and functioning of reproductive organs etc. There are rare cases of poisoning Zn. His action in aquatic fauna depends on the hardness of water, saturated with oxygen and temperature. Salts of alkaline-earth elements reduce the toxicity of Zn, while the increasing of temperature and the lowering of concentration of dissolved oxygen increase the toxicity of the Zn.

Cu-is rare ingredient of natural waters. He can catch in water from the use of Cu pipes or dosing tanks with copper sulphate (II), which is used to prevent the growth of algae. It is proved that Cu is toxic to fish and other aquatic creatures, in those concentrations that do not pose a risk to man. It is known that ion of Cu (II) is mainly poisonous chemical element. Copper is important for human life and other living things so he plays an important role in metabolic processes, it affects a number of enzymes and hemoglobin synthesis. Toxicity of Cu in water depends on the alkalinity, pH value, the content of organic substances, etc. With the increase of these parameters the concentration of ions of Cu (II) decreases and Cu toxicity to aquatic systems.

Pb is also heavy metal that in aquatic environments appears to be able in +2 oxidation and comes from various industrial sources and mines. Pb from gasoline (with tetraethyl lead), is the main source of atmospheric Pb and a large part of his passes in the water. Otherwise rarely detected in natural waters. Pb is also poisonous metal. Poisoning people with Pb causes disturbances in the functioning of the kidneys, reproductive system, liver and nervous system. Pb poisoning made by environmental

exposure that causes mental retardation to more children, while mild poisoning has lead to anemia. Lack of Ca, Fe, Cu, Se and ascorbic acid in food conditions the accumulation of lead in the body. The largest amount of Pb accumulates is in the bones (around 90%) and it replaces Ca. Pb organic compounds easily reach the human body through the skin and central nervous system at risk. Toxic action of Pb is also based on the great affinity to sulfur. Pb reduces the activity of enzymes, oxidation-reduction reactions in the cell and protein synthesis. It is known that Pb poisoning is greater in strong waters than in temperate waters.

Cd - as pollutants in the water can reach from industrial discharges and waste ore. It is widely used in galvanization and production of batteries. Cd is chemically similar to Zn and found water in the form +2 oxidation. It occurs naturally as CdS and followed minerals and Pb Zn. Food is the main source of Cd poisoning. Water during the day, one gets only about 10% of Cd. Effects of acute Cd poisoning in humans are very serious as high blood pressure, kidney damage, causing potential prostate cancer etc. Performed by the physiological effects of Zn with Cd replacement in some enzymatic reactions and so hampered normal functioning of enzymes. Toxic effect of Cd in water decreases with increasing hardness of the water, due to rising water carbonates. Heavy metal carbonates are less soluble in water and so a part of dissolved Cd removed from the water.

3.2. The results of the research

The results of measurements of this research are presented in Tables 3, 4 dhe5 and Figure 3. In this research is monitored for one year the heavy metals (Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd) in the waters of the river Shkumbin and there were no serious levels pollution with them. Their content is accompanied by APS, while some results of this method are verified by SAA. Results of the verification measurements of heavy metals that are made with atomic absorber September 2002 are given in Table 5.

Table 3. APS experimental results with the averages for the content of Zn in Shkumbin river waters expressed in mg / L

Month / Place sampling	SH1	SH2	SH3	SH4	monthly averages:
January	0.0180	0.0220	0.0286	0.0352	0.0260
February	0.0140	0.0263	0.0374	0.0382	0.0290
March	0.0116	0.0124	0.0235	0.0357	0.0208
April	0.0624	0.0624	0.0624	0.0748	0.0655
May	0.0200	0.0150	0.0150	0.0080	0.0145
June	0.0090	0.0090	0.0060	0.0090	0.0083
July	0.0210	0.0220	0.0180	0.0260	0.0218
August	0.0206	0.0092	0.0192	0.0150	0.0160
September	0.0100	0.0090	0.0130	0.0230	0.0138

October	0.0123	0.0129	0.0263	0.0326	0.0210
November	0.0126	0.0135	0.0176	0.0372	0.0202
December	0.0118	0.0126	0.0158	0.0248	0.0163
Average of Place sampling:	0.0186	0.0189	0.0236	0.0300	Annual average:
					0.0227

* The contents of Cu, Pb and Zn in the river Shkumbin in all the monitoring period is not detected (n.d.)

From the results of PSA it was found that the waters of the river Shkumbin has been more restrained in Zn, while the Cd, Cu and Pb were not detected at all i.e. their content was below the limit of detection of APS (Tab. 3 and Fig. 3). This shows that Shkumbin river waters have been polluted with little heavy metals according to European Regulation and the official Rules of the Republic of Macedonia and they are categorized into first class water.

Table 4. Seasonal and annual statistics of the results of Zn

Winter		Spring		Summer		Autumn		Annual statistics	
Minimum	0.0116	Minimum	0.0060	Minimum	0.0090	Minimum	0.0118	Minimum	0.0060
Maximum	0.0382	Maximum	0.0748	Maximum	0.0260	Maximum	0.0372	Maximum	0.0748
Median	0.0249	Median	0.0150	Median	0.0186	Median	0.0147	Median	0.0180
Average	0.0252	Average	0.0294	Average	0.0172	Average	0.0192	Average	0.0227
Stan. Dev.	0.0099	Stan. Dev.	0.0271	Stan. Dev.	0.0058	Stan. Dev.	0.0088	Stan. Dev.	0.0157
Sum	0.3029	Sum	0.3530	Sum	0.2060	Sum	0.2300	Sum	1.0919
N / Count	12	N / Count	48						
Range	0.0116-0.0382	Range	0.0060-0.0748	Range	0.0090-0.0260	Range	0.0118-0.0372	Range	0.0060-0.0748

Table 5. The content of heavy metals in the river Shkumbin measured by SAA in September 2002, expressed in mg / L

Place sampling	Zn (mg/L)	Cu (mg/L)	Pb (mg/L)	Cd (mg/L)
SH1	< 0.09	< 0.1	< 0.1	< 0.1
SH2	< 0.12	< 0.1	< 0.1	< 0.1
SH3	< 0.13	< 0.1	< 0.1	< 0.1
SH4	< 0.15	< 0.1	< 0.1	< 0.1

3.3. Discussion of results for zinc

Annual results: Zn has been present in the waters of the river Shkumbin. The average annual content of Zn standard deviation was 0.0227 ± 0.0157 mg / L, while the annual range was 0.0060-0.0748 mg Zn / L. Higher concentrations of Zn were recorded in April and had a range of 0.0624-0.0478 mg / L, while concentrations were measured lower in June with an interval of extension of 0.0060-0.0090 mg / lower L. The value measured in SH3 (0.0624 mg / L) in June and November it higher on SH4 (0.0478 mg / L) in April. Averages of months: January, February, March, April, May, June, July, August, September, October, November and December were: 0.0260 mg / L, 0.0290 mg / L, 0.0208 mg / L, 0.0655 mg / L, 0.0145 mg / L, 0.0083 mg / L, 0.0218 mg / L, 0.0160 mg / L, 0.0138 mg / L, 0.0210 mg / L, 0.0202 mg / L and 0.0163 mg / L, respectively. The month with the lowest average was in June (0.0083 mg / L), while the highest monthly average in April (0.0655 mg / L). Site-sampling averages were: SH1 (0.0186 mg / L), SH2 (0.0189 mg / L), SH3 (0.10236 mg / L) and SH4 (0.0300 mg / L). The average value was lower on SH1, while it higher in SH4 (Tab. 3, 4 and Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Time and space variation of the content of Zn in the river Shkumbin

Results in winter: standard deviation average content of Zn in the winter season was 0.0252 ± 0.0099 mg / L, while the extent of Zn was 0.0116-0.0382 mg / L. The lowest value was measured on SH1 (0.0116 mg / L) in March and it highest on SH4 (0.0382 mg / L) in February. Average values of January, February and March were: 0.0260 mg / L, 0.0290 mg / L and 0.0208 mg / L respectively. The month with the lowest average was in March (0.0208 mg / L), while the highest average was February (0.0290 mg / L). Site-sampling averages were: SH1 (0.0145 mg / L), SH2 (0.0202 mg / L), SH3 (0.0298 mg / L) and SH4 (0.0364 mg / L). The average value was lower on SH1, while it higher in SH4 (Tab. 3, 4 and Fig. 3).

Results in spring: the average standard deviation content of Zn in spring was 0.0294 ± 0.0271 mg / L, while the extent of Zn was 0.0060-0.0748 mg / L. The lowest value was measured in SH3 (0.0060mg / L) in June and November it higher on SH4 (0.0748 mg / L) in April. Average values of April, May and June were: 0.0655 mg / L, 0.0145 mg / L and 0.0083 mg / L respectively. The month with the lowest average has been June (0.0083 mg / L), while the highest average was in April (0.0655 mg / L). Site-sampling averages were: SH1 (0.0305 mg / L), SH2 (0.0288 mg / L), SH3 (0.0278 mg / L) and SH4 (0.0306 mg / L). The average value was lower on SH3, while it higher for SH4 (Tab. 3, 4 and Fig. 3).

Results in the summer: the average standard deviation content of Zn in the summer was 0.0058 ± 0.0172 mg / L, while the extent of Zn was 0.0090-0.0260 mg / L. The lowest value was measured in November SH2 in September and it higher on SH4 in July. The average values of the months July, August and September were: 0.0218 mg / L, 0.0160 mg / L and 0.0138 mg / L respectively. The month with the lowest average was September (0.0138 mg / L), while the highest average was in July (0.0218 mg / L). Site-sampling averages were: SH1 (0.0172 mg / L), SH2 (0.0134 mg / L), SH3 (0.0167 mg / L) and SH4 (0.0213 mg / L). The average value was lower on SH2, while it higher for SH4 (Tab. 3, 4 and Fig. 3).

Results in the autumn: the standard deviation average content of Zn in the autumn was 0.0192 ± 0.0088 mg / L, while the extent of Zn was 0.0118-0.0372 mg / L. The lowest value was measured in SH1 in December and it SH4 higher in November. The average values of the months October, November and December were: 0.0210 mg / L, 0.0202 mg / L and 0.0163 mg / L respectively. The month with the lowest average was December (0.0163 mg / L), while the highest average was in October (0.0210 mg / L). Site-sampling averages were: SH1 (0.0122 mg / L), SH2 (0.0130 mg / L), SH3 (0.0199 mg / L) and SH4 (0.0315 mg / L). The average value was lower on SH1, while it higher in SH4 (Tab. 3, 4 and Fig. 3).

Viewed as a whole, water pollution of the river Shkumbin is smaller in two first sampling points (SH1 and SH2), while the largest sampling of the third (SH3) and

fourth (SH4) - before pouring the river Shkumbin River to Vardar. Higher pollution in the last two-day sampling points that resulted from: runoff water from the river; regional erosion from rainfall; urban settlements from the waters that flow going towards the last river are increasing more; medical and pharmaceutical chemicals as waste from the city hospital; by wastewater plant mentioned city (although they operate with reduced) and the general pollution of the environment in the area of the municipality of Tetovo.

4. Conclusion

In this one-year research was conducted monitoring of the degree of pollution of the river Shkumbin of the city of Tetovo with heavy metals: Zn, Cu, Pb and Cd. Metals mentioned are determined by APS, APS and some results have been verified by SAA. According to the results obtained by APS showed that Shkumbin river waters have been the first category under the European Regulation and the official Rules of the Republic of Macedonia and they have not been contaminated.

According to the results of measurements, samples of water place sampling view - SH1 (at village Brodec) and samples taken in the second - SH2 (Banja Hisar, under Sellce and Shipkovic villages) were less contaminated with Zn. Samples of water third place sampling - SH3 (under hospital in Tetovo) were more contaminated with Zn than those place sampling in SH1 and SH2. The last place sampling water - SH4 (the village Saracine, 0.5 km prior to discharge into the river Vardar Shkumbin) have been charged with Zn (Tab. 3, 4 and Fig. 3).

From the results we can conclude that Shkumbin river waters have a higher content of Zn in the village Saracino, ie after leaving the city until his discharge in the river Vardar. For the period researched, Shkumbin river can still be considered unpolluted and it features an aquatic ecosystem suitable for life to exist as well as the different activities and economic life. However, during the monitoring in the first year often there have been different metal waste in the river and its pellgune. This, in fact, have been a way of river pollution with heavy metals, which indicates a low level of ecological culture of the population. Therefore, we recommend relevant institutions to contribute as much as they can to the growth of environmental awareness in order to be protected from pollution Shkumbin river - one of the natural resources in the region of Tetovo.

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